

IntegrateMind: A Multidisciplinary Journal

To Cite:

Alagbe, J. O. Phytochemical Analysis and Bioactive Profiling of Clerodendron Splendens Leaf Extract by GC/MS. *IntegrateMind: A Multidisciplinary Journal* 2024; Vol 2, Issue 1, pp. 75-81.

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Peer-Review History

Received: 11th March, 2024

Reviewed & Revised: 12/March / 2024 to 3rd April/2024

Accepted: 5th April 2024

Published: 7th April 2024

Peer-Review Model

External peer-review was done through double-blind method.

IntegrateMind: A Multidisciplinary Journal

ISSN: xxxx-xxxx

URL: <https://sites.google.com/view/sherwanjournals/integratemind-journal>

Ethics

No animal studies are presented in this manuscript.

No human studies are presented in this manuscript.

No potentially identifiable human images or data is presented in this study.

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Phytochemical Analysis and Bioactive Profiling of Clerodendron Splendens Leaf Extract by GC/MS

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ABSTRACT

Plants generally contain complex mixtures of biologically active secondary metabolites with multiple target effects and often low toxicity. This study was carried to evaluate the phytochemical analysis and bioactive profiling of Clerodendron splendens leaf extract by GC/MS. Phytochemical analysis of Clerodendron splendens leaf extract reveals the presence of phenol (512.66 mg/100g), saponins (277.81mg/100g), flavonoids (944.10 mg/100g), terpenoids (610.82 mg/100g), alkaloids (1615.9 mg/100g), tannins (1026.1 mg/100g) and steroids (11.52 mg/100g). GC/MS characterization of Clerodendron splendens leaf extract reveals the presence of 19 bioactive compounds namely: 2-propanoic acid, 2 propanyl ester is the major compound which contained 20.11 % followed by 10-Azido-1-decanethiol (18.22 %), squalene (18.06 %), 3,4 dimethyl 5 hexen 3-ol (10.73 %), 2-dimethyl silyoxytridecane (10.40 %), 2 - Hydroxypropanenitrite (5.33 %), 1-Nonene, 4,6,8 - trimethyl (5.09 %), Isooctanol (2.51 %), 1-Hepten-4-ol (1.84 %), 3-Butyn-2-ol (1.67 %), 2-Octyl-6-Octadecanoic acid (1.33 %), 9- Propen-1-amine (1.22 %), 1,14 - Tetradecanediol (0.84 %), Hexanedioic acid -bis-2 ethylhexyl (0.56 %), Di-methyl urethane (0.21 %), 3-Pentanol, 2,4 dimethyl (0.09 %), Ethyl 9-decenoate (0.06 %), 1 - Fluorooctane (0.05 %) and 3 - butyn-2-ol (0.02 %). In conclusion, Clerodendron splendens leaf extract is rich in several bioactive compounds with several pharmacological properties which can be utilized as natural alternative to antibiotics in livestock production.

Keywords: Phytochemicals, Clerodendron splendens, Bioactive compounds, Therapeutic properties, Gas chromatography.

1. INTRODUCTION

Plants have the ability to produce a wide variety of chemical substances. These chemicals are divided into primary and secondary metabolites (Yakov, 2006). Primary metabolites such as sugar and fats are found in all plants but secondary metabolites are produced in small range of plants which have specific functions (Nuraliev, 2008; Shahat et al., 2011). Each plant species on earth produces a number of specific secondary metabolites (Nganso et al., 2018). In addition, there are a number factors such as climate, soil, season, environment, pesticides, fertilizers, plant disease, age and etc. whole affect to the quality and quantity of secondary metabolites (Alagbe, 2024c; Alagbe et al., 2022). Medicinal plants generally contain complex mixtures of biologically active compounds (Farukh, 2015). They affect multiple targets. In general, plants used in phytotherapy show low toxicity. Some of the active secondary metabolites can have advantages in treating chronic diseases (Amal, 2014).

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Clerodendron splendens commonly called flaming glory bower is an evergreen, woody stemmed vine belonging to the family Lamiaceae (Gbedma et al., 2010). It is widely distributed in tropical and subtropical regions of the world (Oppong, 2014). The leaves and barks are used in traditional medicine to treat coughs, buboes problem, sexually transmitted infections, gastro intestinal infections, skin diseases, scrofulous infection, amongst others (Shirivastiva and Petel, 2007). Diabete et al. (2022) reported that *Clerodendron splendens* leaves, stem bark and root contains biologically active compounds, such as alkaloids, glucosinolates, cyanogenic glucosides, flavonoids, tannins, coumarins, lignans, terpenoids, saponins, organic acids, and many others (Apak et al., 2013). According to Afoulous et al. (2013); Abdallah and Ezzat (2011), methanolic and ethanolic extracts from the leaves of *Clerodendron splendens* have the capacity to inhibit the activities of *Shigella flexneri*, *Salmonella typhi*, *Proteus mirabilis*, *Pseudomonas aeruginosa*, *Klebsiella pneumonia*, *Enterococcus faecalis*, *Listeria monocytogenes* and *Bacillus cereus* due to the presence of phytochemicals like phenols, tannins and flavonoids which have been suggested to perform multiple biological activities against pathogenic organisms (Ivaceheva et al., 2006). Root extracts from *Clerodendron splendens* have been reported to exhibit important biological activities including antibacterial, antimicrobial and antifungal activities (Ivacheva et al., 2006).

The biosynthesis of secondary metabolites in medicinal and aromatic plants is strongly influenced by environmental factors ((Alagbe, 2024c). Therefore, this experiment was carried to examine the phytochemical analysis and bioactive profiling of *Clerodendron splendens* leaf extract by GC/MS.

2. MATERIALS AND METHODS

2.1. Site of the experiment

The research was carried out at the department of Biochemistry and Microbiology, Sumitra Research Laboratory Gujarat, India located between 23° 13' N and 72° 41' E in the month of September to December, 2023.

2.2. Collection of plant material and preparation of *Clerodendron splendens* extracts

Fresh *Clerodendron splendens* leaves were harvested within Sumitra Research Institute botanical garden in Gujarat and sent to the department of Biological Sciences of the institute where it was identified by a certified crop taxonomist and assigned a voucher number AA/GT/2023A. Leaves were washed with running tap water, placed in a plastic sieve for 10 minutes to allow the water to drain before it was shade dried on a clean flat metallic surface for 10 days to retain the chemical compounds in plants. The dried leaves of *Clerodendron splendens* were ground using an electric blending machine and the powdered samples were packed in a labeled transparent zip lock for further examination and extraction.

200 g of *Clerodendron splendens* powder was weighed into a conical flask containing 1000 mL water and kept for 4 days during which it was stirred intermittently after every 4 hours. The mixture was thereafter filtered through a Whatman filter paper. The extract was evaporated into dryness in a rotary evaporator under reduced pressure at 50°C to obtain *Clerodendron splendens* extract (CSE).

2.3.1. Qualitative analysis of *Clerodendron splendens* extract (CSE)

Qualitative analysis of *Clerodendron splendens* extract is presented in Table 1 and Table 2.

Table 1: Qualitative analysis of *Clerodendron splendens* extract (CSE)

Test	Reagents/chemicals required	Laboratory procedure	Outcome
Mayer's test	Meyer's reagent	Add 2 ml of extract with the help of a dropper into a test tube followed by the addition of few drops of Meyer's reagent.	Formation of a cream precipitate indicates the presence of alkaloids
Wagner's test	Wagner's reagent	Add 2 ml of extract into a test tube then add few drops of Wagner's reagent a keep for few seconds	Formation of reddish brown colour suggests the presence of alkaloids
Hager's test	Hager's reagent	2 ml of extract was transferred into a test tube followed by the addition of few drops of Hager's reagent and kept for few seconds	The formation of yellow precipitate indicates the presence of alkaloids
Dragendroff's test	Dragendroff's reagent	2 ml of extract was transferred into a test tube followed by the addition of Dragendroff's reagent	Orange – red colour was obtained
Shinoda's test	Concentrated hydrochloric acid, magnesium ribbon	2 ml of extract was transferred into a test tube followed by the addition of few drops of concentrated hydrochloric acid then 2 pieces of magnesium ribbon	Purple colour suggest the presence of flavonoid
Alkaline reagent test	Sodium hydroxide, hydrochloric acid	2 ml of extract was transferred into a test tube followed by the addition of few drops of hydrochloric acid then 2 % sodium hydroxide	Intense yellow colour suggests the presence of flavonoids

Test	Reagents/chemicals required	Laboratory procedure	Outcome
Terpenoid's test	Sulphuric acid, chloroform	2 ml of extract was transferred into a test tube followed by the addition of 1 ml of chloroform then 1.5 ml of sulfuric acid using glass pipette	Redish brown colour indicates the presence of terpenoids
Ferric chloride test	Ferric acid solution	Transfer 2 ml of extract into a test tube then add few drops of 5 % ferric chloride solution	Dark green colour indicates the presence of condensed tannins. Dark blue colour suggest the presence of hydrolysable tannins
Lead acetate test	Lead acetate solution	Transfer 2 ml of extract into a test tube then add few drops of lead acetate solution and kept for some seconds	The presence of white precipitate indicates the presence of tannins
Steroid test	Sulfuric acid	2 ml of extract was transferred into a test tube followed by the addition of 2 ml of chloroform then few drops of sulfuric acid along the sides of the tubes with a dropper	Formation of red colour indicates the presence of steroids
Ferric chloride test	Ferric chloride reagent	2 ml of extract was transferred into a test tube followed by the addition of ferric chloride and kept for some seconds	Formation of purple colour indicates the presence of phenols

Table 2: Qualitative results for phytochemicals in *Clerodendron splendens* extract (CSE)

Phytochemicals	Status
Phenols	Present
Saponins	Present
Flavonoids	Present
Terpenoids	Present
Alkaloids	Present
Tannins	Present
Steroids	Present

2.3.2. Quantitative phytochemical analysis of *Clerodendron splendens* extract (CSE)

Quantitative evaluation of *Clerodendron splendens* extract (CSE) was carried out in Table 3, according to the previous method described by ((Alagbe, 2024c).

Table 3: Quantitative analysis of *Clerodendron splendens* extract (CSE)

Components	Composition (mg/100g)
Phenols	512.66
Saponins	277.81
Flavonoids	944.10
Terpenoids	610.82
Alkaloids	1615.9
Tannins	1026.1
Steroids	11.52

2.4. Estimation of total flavonoids

Using catechin as a reference, the total flavonoid content was calculated using the aluminium chloride technique. After adding 0.1 mL of aluminum chloride and 0.2 mL of 5 percent sodium nitrite, 1.5 mL of *Clerodendron splendens* powder (CSE) was added to 3 mL of 1 M sodium hydroxide. The mixture was thoroughly mixed and incubated for 10 minutes at room temperature. Immediately, 10 mL of distilled water were added to the final volume. Using a spectrophotometer, the reaction mixture's absorbance at 550 nm was evaluated in comparison to a blank (Alagbe, 2024c).

2.5. Estimation of total phenols

The Folin-reagent Ciocalteu's was used to determine the total phenolic contents in CSE. 2.0 mL of CSP and 0.4 mL of 1:10 v/w were combined followed by the addition of 4 mL of sodium carbonate solution and kept at room temperature for 15 minutes. A spectrophotometer was used to test the sample's absorbance at 800 nm in comparison to the blank. The phenolic content in the sample was expressed as milligrams of catechol per dry gram of dry weight (Alagbe, 2024c).

2.6. Estimation of total saponins

Using a vanillin and concentrated sulfuric acid colorimetric technique, saponin was quantified. 0.4 milliliters of 77 percent sulfuric acid, 0.5 milliliters of freshly made vanillin solution, and 0.2 milliliters of CSP were combined. The mixture was allowed to cool to

room temperature before being heated in a water bath for 30 minutes at 60 degrees centigrade. A spectrophotometer was used to detect the absorbance at 560 nm (Alagbe, 2024c).

2.7. Total alkaloid concentration

Alkaloids were precipitated by mixing 20 mL of acetic acid solution in ethanol (10 percent w/v) with 1.5 mL of CSE and placing the mixture on a water bath for 10 minutes followed by the addition of ammonium hydroxide. After the precipitate reached a constant weight, it was transferred to desiccators and reweighed to estimate the total alkaloid content (Alagbe, 2024c).

2.8. Total tannins estimation

The Folin-Ciocalteu technique was employed to determine the total tannin concentration. 2.0 mL of sodium bicarbonate and 1.0 mL Folin-Ciocalteu was added to 1 mL of CSE to dilute it (100 mL). The combination was thoroughly mixed and then let to cool for 15 minutes at room temperature. Then, using a spectrophotometer, the absorbance of the standard curve and CSE were compared to a blank at 800 nm (Alagbe, 2024c).

2.9. Estimation of total steroids

2 mL of CSE is transferred into a test tube followed by the addition of 0.5 mL of sodium hydroxide solution and 0.2 mL aluminum oxide and kept for 10 minutes. CSE is observed at an optical density of 350 nm [16].

2.10. GC-MS profiling of *Clerodendron splendens* extract

GC-MS profiling of *Clerodendron splendens* extract was carried out using Aludra gas chromatograph – mass spectrometer (Quadrupole) auto-sampler with fused silica capillary column (30 m × 0.25 mm × 0.25 μm) and MS3200RT software package real time data acquisition application and MS3200P data processing application for easy result interpretation. For effective running of the machine, the gas chromatograph is subjected to a maximum heating rate of 40°C/min and maximum run time of 999.99 minutes, pressure and flow range of 0.999 kpa and 200 mL/min respectively while the mass spectrometer chamber is maintained at a mass range of 1.5 – 1024.0 amu, maximum scan and dynamic range (10,000 amu/s and 105), emission current (10 – 350 μA) (see, Table 4).

Table 4: Bioactive profiling of *Clerodendron splendens* leaf extract (CSE) by GC-MS

Compounds	Retention time	Peak area %	Molecular weight (g/mol)	Molecular formula
3,4 dimethyl 5 hexen 3-ol	9.11	10.73	C ₈ H ₁₆ O	128
1-Nonene, 4,6,8 – trimethyl	10.08	5.09	C ₁₂ H ₂₄	168
Isooctanol	10.55	2.51	C ₈ H ₁₈ O	130
1-Hepten-4-ol	11.73	1.84	C ₇ H ₁₄ O	114
3 – butyn-2-ol	11.80	0.02	C ₄ H ₆ O	70
2-propanoic acid, 2 propanyl ester	11.93	20.11	C ₆ H ₈ O ₂	112
Squalene	12.40	18.06	C ₃₀ H ₅₀	410
1,14 – Tetradecanediol	12.56	0.84	C ₁₄ H ₃₀ O ₂	230
Di-methyl urethane	13.97	0.21	C ₃ H ₇ NO ₂	89.09
Ethyl 9-decenoate	14.21	0.06	C ₁₂ H ₂₂ O	198.30
2-Octyl-6-Octadecanoic acid	14.55	1.33	C ₃₈ H ₇₆ O ₂	565.0
10-Azido-1-decanethiol	14.60	18.22	C ₁₀ H ₂₁ N ₃ S	215.36
1 – Fluorooctane	14.93	0.05	C ₈ H ₁₇ F	132.22
2-dimethyl silyoxytridecane	15.11	10.40	C ₁₉ H ₄₄ OSi ₂	120.8
2 – Hydroxypropanenitrite	16.37	5.33	C ₃ H ₅ NO	70.08
9- Propen-1-amine	17.03	1.22	C ₃ H ₇ N	57.09
Hexanedioic acid –bis-2 ethylhexyl	17.55	0.56	C ₂₂ H ₄₂ O	370
3-Pentanol, 2,4 dimethyl	18.06	0.09	C ₇ H ₁₆ O	116
3-Butyn-2-ol	19.02	1.67	C ₄ H ₆ O	70
Total	-	98.34	-	-

3. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

The preliminary (qualitative) evaluation of *Clerodendron splendens* extract is presented in Table 2 while the quantitative assessment is presented in Table 3. Both results revealed that CSE contains alkaloids (1615.9 mg/100g), saponins (277.81 mg/100g), flavonoids (944.10 mg/100g), tannins (1026.1 mg/100g), terpenoids (610.82 mg/100g), phenols (512.66 mg/100g) and steroids (11.52 mg/100g). This result suggests that CSE contains chemical compounds with therapeutic or medicinal properties. Most alkaloids are believed to function as defensive elements against predators, especially mammals because of their general toxicity and deterrence capability (Ivacheva et al., 2006; Alagbe, 2024b). Several reports have shown that alkaloids exhibit a wide range of pharmacological properties such as: analgesics, antimalarial, anti-inflammatory and immune-stimulatory (Farukh, 2015; Alagbe et al., 2022). Phenolic

compounds are one of the largest groups of secondary plants constituents synthesized by fruits, vegetables, teas, cocoa and other plants that possess certain health benefits. They usually possess an aromatic ring bearing one or more hydroxyl groups and range from simple phenolic molecules to highly polymerized compounds (Alagbe et al., 2024a; Alagbe et al., 2024b). Phenolic compounds have antioxidant, anti-inflammatory, anti-carcinogenic and other biological properties and may prevent oxidative stress (Prior et al., 2005). Tannins are known to have antibacterial, anti-allergic, antioxidant and cardio-protective properties (Alok et al., 2014). Terpenoids are used extensively for their aromatic qualities. Extensive biological investigations have been carried out within the group and these studies have revealed a broad spectrum of pharmacological and physiological properties (Singh et al., 2022; Mawa et al., 2013). They play a role in traditional herbal remedies and are under investigation for antibacterial, antineoplastic, and other pharmaceutical functions. Recent findings demonstrate that certain nitrogenous terpene derivatives possess the potent anti-hypertensive activity and may indicate a new era in medicine through the synthetic terpenoids path (Moradkhani et al., 2012; Agubosi et al., 2012). The antimicrobial and insecticidal properties of other terpenoids have led to their utilization as pesticides and fungicides in agriculture and horticulture (Noorhajati et al., 2012). Flavonoids have antioxidant, anti-inflammatory, antimicrobial and can also help to boost the immune system (Singh et al., 2006). Saponins have a wide pharmacological activities including: antirhythmic, vasodilatory and antimicrobial properties (Trombetta et al., 2005). They are glycoside compounds often referred to as natural detergent because of their foamy nature (Alagbe, 2022). Steroids play a vital role in reproductive activities in animals (Wink, 2012). The result on CSE in this experiment is disagrees with the reports of (Iroabuchi, 2008). These discrepancies can be attributed to differences in geographical location, climate, age of plant and extraction procedures (Agubosi et al., 2022; Musa et al., 2020).

Bioactive profiling of *Clerodendron splendens* leaf extract (CSE) by GC-MS (Table 4) reveals the presence of 19 bioactive compounds comparing their retention time and peak areas. 2-propanoic acid, 2 propanyl ester is the major compound which contained 20.11 % followed by 10-Azido-1-decanethiol (18.22 %), squalene (18.06 %), 3,4 dimethyl 5 hexen-3-ol (10.73 %), 2-dimethyl silyoxytridecane (10.40 %), 2-Hydroxypropanenitrite (5.33 %), 1-Nonene, 4,6,8-trimethyl (5.09 %), Isooctanol (2.51 %), 1-Hepten-4-ol (1.84 %), 3-Butyn-2-ol (1.67 %), 2-Octyl-6-Octadecanoic acid (1.33 %), 9-Propen-1-amine (1.22 %), 1,14-Tetradecanediol (0.84 %), Hexanedioic acid-bis-2 ethylhexyl (0.56 %), Di-methyl urethane (0.21 %), 3-Pentanol, 2,4 dimethyl (0.09 %), Ethyl 9-decenoate (0.06 %), 1-Fluorooctane (0.05 %) and 3-butyn-2-ol (0.02 %). These compounds have several pharmacological properties for instance, 2-Octyl-6-Octadecanoic acid and 2-propanoic acid, 2 propanyl ester found in CSE is reported to have antimicrobial and anti-inflammatory properties (Herbdatabase, 2014). Ivancheva et al. (2006); Jin et al. (2012) reported that Hexanedioic acid-bis-2 ethylhexyl, 10-Azido-1-decanethiol and 1,14-Tetradecanediol possess antimicrobial and antidiarrheal properties. Squalene is reported to have anti-inflammatory and antioxidant activity (Keawsaard et al., 2012; Knapp et al., 1967). (Maggi et al., 2014) reported that 3-Pentanol, 2,4 dimethyl have antifungal, immune-stimulatory and antimicrobial properties. Several of these metabolites have therapeutic properties and their concentration in the plant tissues is considered as the main factor to evaluate the therapeutic value and quality of a given herb (Adewale et al., 2021; Musa et al., 2020).

4. CONCLUSIONS

In conclusion, *Clerodendron splendens* leaf extract is loaded with several phytochemicals with pharmacological properties viz: antimicrobial, antiviral, anti-inflammatory, antimutagenic, antinociceptive, antipyretic, antispasmodic, antithrombotic, apoptotic, cardiovascular, chemomodulatory, antitumor, hepatoprotective, hypoglycemic, hypolipidemic, and memory enhancing properties. This phyto-constituents are eco-friendly and effective and could be used as natural alternative to antibiotics in livestock production.

Ethical approval

All international standards have been adopted and compliance.

Informed consent

The study was conducted with equal participation by all authors.

Conflicts of interests

The authors declare that there are no conflicts of interests.

Funding

The study has not received any external funding.

Data and materials availability

All data associated with this study are present in the paper.

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